

Intersecting Realms : Malocclusion Nexus with Temporomandibular Disorder Pathway

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Abstract

AIM: To assess the relationship between TMDs and malocclusion.
Material & Methods: Temporomandibular dysfunction was assessed in 120 patients using the Helkimo Dysfunction Index (Di) (1974). **RESULT :** The incidence of TMD may not be predicted by age; most women experience mild symptoms, but men rarely do; The majority of severe instances are in females, and Class II malocclusions exhibit severe symptoms.
Conclusion: Our study of 120 patients revealed that mild TMD is the most common category for both genders and that TMD is more common in women. Although there is no clear correlation between Class I malocclusion and TMD, it may play a role in its development.
Keywords : Temporomandibular disorders, Class II, Malocclusion, Helkimo Dysfunction Index (Di).

Introduction

The temporomandibular joint (TMJ), a hinge joint on each side of the face, allows you to talk and chew without restriction. This joint allows the jaw to move freely when speaking and chewing. The jaw's position and movements are controlled by the muscles surrounding and attached to the joint.¹ Although the precise origin of temporomandibular dysfunction is still unknown, a number of variables are thought to be involved. Malocclusion is often identified as one of these causes, along with parafunctional behaviours and joint hyperlaxity, as the primary cause.² Incorrect alignment of the jaw along the sagittal plane can cause malocclusion, which can be impacted by mandibular dysplasia, vertical jaw dysplasia, or a combination of the two.³ TMJ examination is crucial for malocclusion diagnosis since certain malocclusion features might lead to joint dysfunctions.³ There aren't many research in the literature about TMD prevalence in those who have malocclusion. Thus, the purpose of this study is to evaluate how malocclusion affects the frequency of bruxism and TMD.

Methodology

A cohort of 120 people who had visited Nims Dental College and Hospital in Jaipur were the subjects of the current investigation. Using the Helkimo dysfunction index (Di), a screening for temporomandibular dys

function was performed on each participant. Three levels of severity were used to evaluate each domain: 0 for no symptoms, 1 for mild symptoms, and 5 for acute symptoms. A total dysfunction score ranging from 0 to 25 points was obtained by calculating the cumulative scores; higher scores denoted a higher degree of temporomandibular dysfunction.

Group Categorization

Group 1: Patients with Malocclusion and no Temporomandibular dysfunction.
Group 2: Patients with Malocclusion and Temporomandibular dysfunction.

Clinical Evaluations:

HELKIMO DYSFUNCTIONAL CLINICAL INDEX (1974)		
A. Symptom:	Limiting movement	
Criterion:	No limitation	0
	Modest limitation	1
	Severe limitation	5
B. Symptom:	Limitation of ATM functionality	
Criterion:	Regular movement without joint noise and detour to open or close <2mm	0
	Joint noises in one or both joints and/or deviation >2mm opening or closing	1
	Locking and/or dislocation of ATM.	5
C. Symptom:	Muscle pain	
Criterion:	No palpation pain	0
	Pain in 1-3 sites palpated	1
	Pain in 4 or more palpated sites	5
D. Symptom:	Pain at ATM	
Criterion:	No palpation pain	0
	Pain at side palpation	1
	Pain at the rear palpation	5
E. Symptom:	Pain during jaw movements	
Criterion:	No pain	0
	Pain during a movement	1
	Pain during two or more movements	5

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Fig 1: TMJ assessment.

Fig 3: Masseter Muscle Palpation.

Fig 4 : Temporalis muscle assessment.

Fig 2: Mouth opening assessment.

Fig 5 : Muscle palpation in the occipital Region.

Fig 6: Intraoral photographs to assess type of Malocclusion.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was coded and entered in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Subsequently, analysis was performed using SPSS version 20 (IBM SPSS Statistics Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA) on a Windows software program.

Normality Assessment

The variables underwent assessment for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to ascertain adherence to a normal distribution.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were computed to provide an overview of the data: This included the calculation of percentages, means, and standard deviations, offering a summary of the central tendency and dispersion of the variables.

Significance Level: A predetermined level of significance was set at a P-value less than or equal to 0.05. This threshold was used to determine statistical significance in the analyses performed. Upon completion of the statistical analyses, the findings provided insights into the distribution, central tendency, and significance of the variables under investigation, allowing for robust conclusions and implications based on the study outcomes.

Result

Figure 1 Distribution of TMDs in various age groups TMDs.

Figure 2 Gender wise distribution of various TMD.

Figure 3 Malocclusion * TMD.

Figure 1 shows intriguing trends in the prevalence of TMD in various age groups. TMD is most common in people 19 and 20 years old (17.6% and 23.5%, respectively). On the other hand, the lowest occurrence is found among those who are 18 and 22 years old, at 0.0% and 0.0%, respectively. There is a marginal rise in the incidence of TMD among adults 25 years of age or older (11.8%). Nevertheless, no distinct linear pattern is visible for any age group. Given the absence of a distinct linear trend, age may not be a reliable indicator of TMD prevalence in this cohort. This idea is further supported by the non-significant p-value (p=0.48), which suggests that age may not be the only factor influencing the observed difference in TMD occurrence.

Significant differences in TMD severity between male and female subjects are shown in Figure 2. Just 18.2% of females had no TMD symptoms (severity level 0), compared to the majority (81.8%) who have mild TMD (severity level 1). On the other hand, fewer men (44.4%) report having no symptoms of TMD, while 55.6% report having mild symptoms. Moreover, 94.1% of severe TMD cases (severity level 2) occur in females, who constitute the majority of cases in this gender group. There is a high correlation between gender and the severity of TMD, as seen by the significant p-value (p=0.001).

Figure 3 illustrates the notable differences in TMD severity among various malocclusion types. 49.4% of people with Class I malocclusion have no TMD symptoms (severity level 0), compared to mild (severity level 1) and severe (severity level 2) symptoms in 22.7% and 0.0% of cases, respectively. On the other hand, 82.4% of people with Class II Div 1 malocclusion have severe TMD symptoms, which is a higher frequency of symptoms. In a similar vein, those with Class II Div 2 malocclusion have a high incidence of severe TMD symptoms (82.4%), but a significant fraction of those with Class III malocclusion experience mild (27.3%) and severe (11.8%) TMD symptoms. The significant p-value (p=0.001) suggests a considerable correlation between the severity of TMD and the type of malocclusion.

Discussion

This study's main goal was to find out how malocclusion affects the frequency of temporomandibular disorders (TMD).

According to our research, the prevalence of TMD symptoms in men was found to be 25.8%, whereas in women it was 38.1%. This is consistent with other research by Hirsch et al., De Oliveria et al., and LeResche, which also found that women had a higher frequency of TMD symptoms. Hormonal differences have been suggested as a possible causative element for gender differences, although the precise cause of these differences is yet unknown.

Based on the Fonseca rating system, which divides TMD symptoms into mild, moderate, and severe categories, the majority of patients (71%), followed by moderate instances (13.7%), had mild TMD. Research by Bagis et al., Dekon et al., Pedroni et al., De Oliveria, and Boniardim et al. is in line with this conclusion.

Various research conducted in the past few decades have offered differing opinions regarding the cause-and-effect

link between TMD and malocclusions. Observing improvements in painful symptoms after adjustments to occlusion, especially in the vertical dimension, Costen (1934) was among the first to propose a link between occlusion and discomfort in the temporomandibular joint (TMJ). Based on MRI investigations, Schellas et al. postulated that ATM pathology may cause malocclusions rather than the other way around. This highlights the significance of assessing TMJ pathology prior to treating malocclusions, which may need orthognathic surgery.

Comparing skeletal Class II (or extreme overjet) malocclusions to other dental abnormalities, several studies have found a higher frequency of TMD in these cases.

On the other hand, Reynders et al. and Seligman and Pullinger came to the conclusion that there was no proof, either scientific or otherwise, linking occlusion to TMD. The contradicting data most likely results from methodological variations in sample qualities, malocclusion recording detail levels, and TMD symptom evaluation amongst research. In light of these results, physicians should take into account certain indicators of malocclusion while performing a clinical examination on patients with TMJ disorders, taking into account the intricate and varied nature of the correlation between malocclusion and TMD symptoms.

Conclusion

It may be concluded from our current study that women had a significantly higher incidence of temporomandibular joint disorder (TMD) among 120 individuals. The most often seen category, for both male and female participants, was mild TMD. Notably, Class II malocclusion is thought to be a contributing factor to TMD but is not directly linked to the condition.

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